

Landing Site Seeker: an Automation of Initial Landing Site Search for Future Lunar Missions.

S. J. Boazman¹, T. Pons², J. M. Gracia¹, and S. Casanova². ¹ispace, Japan, Sumitomo Fudosan Hamacho Building 3F, 3-42-3 Japan, s-boazman@ispace-inc.com, ¹ispace EUROPE S.A., 5G Rue de l'Industrie, 1811 Luxembourg Hollerich. t-pons@ispace-inc.com

Introduction:

In recent years there has been a renewed interest in landing on the Moon, and within the upcoming years there are several planned missions both from space agencies and commercial companies. In addition some missions have been recently completed, in the last few years. There are several areas of interest being targeted for scientific exploration; including but not limited to; the lunar far side, (for developing the understanding of the South Pole Aitken basin and lunar far side geology [1]), Grusthenian domes, (for understanding the composition of these domes and the unique lunar volcanology that has occurred there, [2]) and the south polar region of the Moon, (due to permanently shadowed regions (PSRs), that have colder temperatures and may harbour potential volatiles, [e.g. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]). In the near future other areas may be explored either as landing sites or as lunar bases [e.g. 9].

Previously remote sensing methods with Geographical Information Software (GIS) with a range of planetary datasets (e.g. elevation map, slope map, and optical images) have been used to select a landing site for future lunar missions. The process of landing site selection has been manual within GIS software, applying filters or inbuilt toolboxes to apply requirements (e.g. slopes, elevation ranges, number of hazards) and combine datasets together. Identifying locations which meet the mission requirements then down selecting where necessary [e.g. 10, 11, 12, 13].

Method:

With the increase in number of missions to the Moon, an efficient site selection process is required. We are developing an automated method using python with lunar datasets to identify locations where mission requirements are met, which could then be further investigated. The tool allows for mission requirements (such as slopes, terrain requirements, roughness) to be included as an input, as well as the latitude and longitude range or specific area being investigated as an input. The tool then automatically filters datasets using GIS functions or our own developed functions to ensure the mission requirements are met. The tool allows for time-dependent datasets (Earth visibility and solar illumination maps) to be included, allowing landing site locations to be identified that are compatible for specific mission windows. The output of the tool is a raster file showing the areas that are compatible with the mission requirements specified for the input area (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Simplified flow chart of the landing site seeker tool workflow.

Discussion and Future work:

This new method of site selection increases the efficiency of the first stages of site selection and allows more time for down selection and detailed analysis of the landing site (e.g. hazard analysis, geological studies). The tool can be applied for any region of the Moon that is being targeted by a future mission and can be used for a range of scales, for a latitude range or for whole Moon studies. This allows for a database to be built up of potential landing sites that meet specific mission requirements, for a wide range of latitudes.

In future the tool can be developed to include further analysis such as proximity analysis of potential landing areas to certain geological features such as boulders, craters, PSR, lava tubes and other features of interest. The tool can also add in filtering of other raster layers for specific missions such as mineralogy or thermal raster layers.

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